

Biotransformation Products of (5*R*)-(+)-Pulegone and (2*S*,5*R*)-(-)-Menthone Produced by Cultured Cells of *Catharanthus roseus*[†]

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Catharanthus roseus cultured cells produce several new oxidized products from (5*R*)-(+)-pulegone and (2*S*,5*R*)-(-)-menthone, in some of which a double bond migration has occurred. Products were identified using NMR and mass spectrometry. The pleasant fragrances of some of the products suggest possible use as perfumery agents.

Catharanthus roseus produces the anticancer drugs vincristine and vinblastine^{1,2}, and callous cell cultures have been prepared to study biosynthesis of these compounds. In the course of these studies, it has been found that enzymes present in the culture medium are capable of performing oxidation reactions on a variety of substrates²⁻⁶. As the procedure is simple and the products have possible uses as fragrances or medicinals, further studies have been performed. The present work describes our studies of the biotransformation products produced from (2*S*,5*R*)-(-)-menthone **1**, 5-methyl-2-(1-methylethyl)cyclohexanone⁷ and (5*R*)-(+)-pulegone **2**, 5-methyl-2-(1-methylethylidene)cyclohexanone⁸, a pleasantly fragrant component of oil of pennyroyal.

two and four major components respectively. Preparative gas chromatography afforded pure samples for analysis, which were identified by NMR and mass spectroscopy. The first two components analyzed, **3** and **4**, were those obtained from biotransformation of menthone. The ¹³C spectrum of component **3**, showed a tetrasubstituted double bond, a ketone, two methylenes, two methines, one of which had attached oxygen, and three methyl groups. ¹H NMR showed one doublet methyl and two methyls on unsaturated positions as in pulegone. The coupling pattern indicated that the hydroxy group was at position-2. Component **4** resembled **3**, but had a second double bond in place of the hydroxyl group as indicated in the ¹³C spectrum. The ¹H spectrum showed three methyls at vinyl positions, indicating the structure was as shown.

Component **5**, the first derived from pulegone, also was hydroxylated as indicated by the ms, but the presence of a vinyl proton signal and a protonated vinyl ¹³C signal indicated that a double bond migration had occurred. In the ¹H spectrum, two of the methyl groups were singlets, indicating that the hydroxylation was at the isopropyl position. Components **6** and **7** were difficult to separate and a second chromatography step was necessary. Spectra were similar, indicating that hydroxylation had taken place in the 3-position, giving a mixture of isomers. Determination of their relative stereochemistries relied on coupling constant data for the hydrogen on the hydroxyl position, and comparison with bond angles determined by molecular modeling. Component **6** had small coupling constants of around 3 Hz while component **7** had constants of 6 Hz, and comparison with values derived from the Karplus equation gave stereochemistries as shown. Component **8** had an additional oxygen as shown by ms. ¹³C NMR spectroscopy showed two carbonyl groups, at higher field than found in previous spectra, indicating conjugation. One of the methyl groups was miss-

Fig. 1. Chemical structures, numbering scheme and ¹³C assignments of pulegone and menthone biotransformation products.

After incubation, extracts of the cultures were analyzed by gas chromatography. The fractions were found to have

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

ing, but other features were as in pulegone. Oxidation of one methyl group to an acid was therefore indicated. Due to effects noted on chemical shifts, it is believed that the acid group is on the same side of the molecule as the original carbonyl allowing hydrogen bonding, but this did not lead to the expected ROESY peak between the remaining methyl singlet and the adjacent protons of the ring, so the assignment remains tentative. ^{13}C spectral data is included on the structures and proton assignments are given in the experimental. In cases where peaks are not well separated, assignment of vinyl carbons or isopropyl methyls may be reversed.

The products from these incubations are somewhat more complex than those from our earlier *C. roseus* studies in which vinyl hydroxylation was the only reaction. In the case of menthone, dehydration of products was indicated. The exocyclic double bond caused products to resemble pulegone, but it is probable that hydroxylation in the 6-position occurred first, then in the 2-position, with initial dehydration at the 2-position, as any other mechanism would go through a pulegone intermediate and give pulegone metabolites. The double bond migration in the first pulegone product would be expected in a radical process which would first involve removal of a hydrogen atom and formation of a delocalized radical which would then be hydroxylated. Oxidation of the methyl group to an acid indicates that the oxidation need not be of saturated carbon. The fragrances of the components were pleasant, especially that of component 7 which is both pulegone- and mint-like.

Experimental

Biotransformation experiments : Callus tissues derived from leaves of *C. roseus* were subcultured for 8 years prior to this study. Aliquots were transplanted to Schenk and Heldibrandt medium (100 ml per 300 ml conical flask) containing 2 ppm 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) and 3% sucrose. The tissues were grown with continuous shaking for 3–5 days at 25° in the light, then 20 mg substrate was administered, and the incubation continued under the same conditions for 5–10 days. Cells were filtered off and immersed in methanol for 1–3 days at room temperature. Solvent was removed and the residue taken up in ether. Callus cells were also extracted with ether, and the combined extracts was dried over magnesium sulfate and filtered. Further purification was done by preparative gas chromatography.

Gas chromatography : Analytical GC was performed on a Hewlett-Packard 5890 capillary FID instrument with a 7683 injector system in splitless mode. A 25 m \times 0.33 mm I.D. vitreous silica BP 1 column was used, He pressure 20 psig, temperature programmed at 60° for 1 min, then to 300°

at 15°/min. Retention times under these conditions are given below. Preparative GC was performed on a Varian 3700 FID instrument with variable ratio vitreous silica splitter system using a 1.83 m \times 4 mm I.D. column. Initial separation was performed using 5% OV17 on Chromosorb G HP, 100–120 mesh, programmed 120–250° at 10°/min. Components 2 and 3 were further separated on a 3% Carbowax 20 M on Chromosorb G HP column, 100–120 mesh, programmed at 120–200° at 10°/min. Fractions were collected in glass capillary tubes using a Brownlee-Silverstein thermal gradient collector⁹.

Mass spectroscopy : Mass spectra were acquired on a Hewlett-Packard 5989B instrument interfaced with a Hewlett Packard 5890 gas chromatograph in E.I. mode with a 70 eV ionization potential, using a 25 m \times 0.22 mm I.D. BP1 vitreous silica column with the temperature program described above. Spectral data consists of relative intensities of the parent peak plus the 10 largest peaks of the spectrum.

NMR spectroscopy : NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker ARX-500 at 500 MHz for ^1H and 125 MHz for ^{13}C . Samples were prepared in 0.5 ml CDCl_3 and 5 mm CH or HCN probes were used for ^{13}C and ^1H observe experiments respectively. ^{13}C assignments were made based on data from 1D, DEPT-90 and 135, and HMQC experiments, and were compared to calculated values. ^1H assignments were made using 1D, double quantum filtered COSY and HMQC data as needed. Chemical shifts were calibrated using solvent peaks set at δ 77 and 7.24 for ^{13}C and ^1H respectively. Chemical shifts are in ppm and coupling constants in Hz. For ease of comparison, all ^1H spectral assignments will use the pulegone numbering system.

Molecular modeling : In order to calculate coupling constants for assignments, models of compounds 2 and 3 were generated using Sybyl 6.3 (Tripos Assoc., St. Louis, MO) software running on Silicon Graphics Indigo R4000 or O2 R5000 computer. All methods used for modeling procedures, result analysis and coupling constant measurement are from the COCCOMUT[©] package developed in our laboratory¹⁰. The lowest energy conformations available to alcohol 3 and diastereomeric alcohols 6 and 7 were obtained by a random incremental pulse search¹¹, a heuristic method best suited for global energy minimum search in small molecules. The geometry was then optimized further using the AM1 semiempirical method¹², and the resulting structures were then used to determine coupling constants according to the Karplus equation without consideration of substituent effects¹³. All molecular mechanics employed the Tripos 6.0 general use force field and Gasteiger-Marsili charges^{14,15}.

Compounds from menthone :

(5*R*,6*S*)-6-Hydroxy-5-methyl-2-(1-methylethylidene)-

cyclohexanone (3) : $^1\text{H NMR}$ [δ , (J)] $\text{H}_{3\alpha}$ 2.14 (1.6, 2.4, 12.8, 15.3), $\text{H}_{3\beta}$ 2.79 (2.8, 4.7, 15.3), $\text{H}_{4\alpha}$ 1.83 (2.8, 3.0, 5.0, 13.6), $\text{H}_{4\beta}$ 1.45 (4.7, 11.8, 12.0, 13.6), H_5 1.75 (3.0, 6.4, 11.1, 11.8), $\text{H}_{6\beta}$ 3.61 (11.1), CH_{3-9} 1.78 (1.6), CH_{3-8} 1.92 (2.4); GC-R.T. 7.32 min; m/z (%) 168 (26), 125 (100), 67 (45), 41 (39), 140 (31), 98 (24), 107 (21), 55 (20), 97 (19), 53 (17).

3-Methyl-6-(1-methylethylidene)cyclohex-2-enone (4) : $^1\text{H NMR}$ [δ , (J)] $\text{H}_{3\alpha,\beta}$ 2.64 (0.3, 1.3, 6.2), $\text{H}_{4\alpha,\beta}$ 2.27 (0.9, 1.4, 6.2), H_6 5.87 (1.4, 1.4), CH_{3-8} 1.83 (0.3), CH_{3-9} 2.07 (0.3, 1.3), CH_{3-10} 1.90 (0.9, 1.4); GC-R.T. 8.66 min; m/z (%) 150 (100), 107 (90), 135 (48), 91 (54), 41 (54), 79 (45), 109 (37), 82 (31), 53 (36), 77 (28), 105 (20).

Compounds from pulegone :

(5R)-5-Methyl-2-(1-hydroxy-1-methylethyl)cyclohex-2-enone (5) : $^1\text{H NMR}$ [δ , (J)] H_3 6.86 (2.1, 5.6), $\text{H}_{4\alpha}$ 2.04 (2.5, 3.7, 5.6, 14.0), $\text{H}_{4\beta}$ 2.45 (2.1, 10.6, 14.0), H_5 2.17 (1.5, 3.7, 6.2, 10.6, 11.6), $\text{H}_{6\alpha}$ 2.12 (1.5, 2.5, 14.0), $\text{H}_{6\beta}$ 2.49 (11.6, 14.0), $\text{CH}_{3-8,9}$ 1.37, CH_{3-10} 1.03 (6.2); GC-R.T. 6.81 min; m/z (%) 168 (1), 153 (100), 43 (88), 97 (72), 41 (55), 55 (53), 135 (51), 69 (50), 111 (47), 59 (45), 79 (41).

(3R,5R)-3-Hydroxy-5-methyl-2-(1-methylethylidene)-cyclohexanone (6) : GC-R.T. 7.77 min; $^1\text{H NMR}$ [δ , (J)] $\text{H}_{3\beta}$ 5.00 (3.0, 3.0), $\text{H}_{4\alpha}$ 2.94 (2.5, 3.0, 3.0, 14.0), $\text{H}_{4\beta}$ 2.07 (3.0, 12.4, 14.0), H_5 2.43 (3.0, 4.3, 6.6, 12.0, 12.4), $\text{H}_{6\alpha}$ 2.51 (2.5, 4.3, 14.8), $\text{H}_{6\beta}$ 1.95 (12.0, 14.8), CH_{3-8} 1.98, CH_{3-9} 1.88, CH_{3-10} 1.00 (6.6); m/z (%) 168 (0), 79 (100), 150 (82), 80 (69), 135 (53), 77 (30), 41 (27), 67 (23), 91 (23), 108 (23), 107 (20).

(3S,5R)-3-Hydroxy-5-methyl-2-(1-methylethylidene)-cyclohexanone (7) : $^1\text{H NMR}$ [δ , (J)] $\text{H}_{3\alpha}$ 4.88 (4.8, 6.2), $\text{H}_{4\alpha}$ 2.21 (2.2, 4.8, 6.8, 13.7), $\text{H}_{4\beta}$ 1.40 (6.2, 12.0, 13.7), H_5 1.88 (5.1, 6.3, 6.8, 6.8, 12.0), $\text{H}_{6\alpha}$ 2.39 (2.2, 5.1, 17.5), $\text{H}_{6\beta}$ 2.16 (6.3, 17.5), CH_{3-8} 1.90, CH_{3-9} 1.95, CH_{3-10} 1.03 (6.8); GC-R.T. 7.90 min; m/z (%) 168 (0), 79 (100), 150 (86), 80 (71), 1345 (56), 41 (28), 65 (19), 91 (25), 108 (25), 67 (24), 107 (21).

(Z)-2-[(4R)-(2-Oxo-4-methyl)cyclohexanylidene]-propanoic acid (8) : $^1\text{H NMR}$ [δ , (J)] $\text{H}_{3\alpha}$ 2.35 (1.2, 1.7,

5.3, 13.8), $\text{H}_{3\beta}$ 2.67 (2.3, 4.5, 13.5), $\text{H}_{4\alpha}$ 1.96 (2.1, 2.3, 5.3, 10.1, 13.7), $\text{H}_{4\beta}$ 1.00 (1.2, 1.2, 4.5, 13.7), H_5 1.97 (1.2, 3.7, 6.8, 10.1, 12.2), $\text{H}_{6\alpha}$ 2.33 (2.1, 3.7, 13.2), $\text{H}_{6\beta}$ 1.25 (12.2, 13.2), CH_{3-9} 1.79 (1.7), CH_{3-10} 0.96 (6.8); GC-R.T. 9.18 min; m/z (%) 182 (5), 154 (100), 67 (69), 139 (62), 81 (55), 109 (53), 41 (39), 137 (29), 53 (28), 55 (27), 43 (21).

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